

#22

Evaluation & Impact Assessment SYSTEM ID

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>INTERROGATING CREATING ADDRESSING</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>Particularly useful at the beginning of a project, then used periodically throughout the interactive innovation process.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Group of approx. 12-15.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>No technical expertise required, although different forms of knowledge are needed to identify wide-ranging elements in the system (in which the project/initiative is operating)).</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>2-3 hrs initially, implemented subsequently periodically.</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>No resources required, apart from basic materials.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tools # 1, 11, 12, 21, 24.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- Create a systems schematic for a project/initiative - what are the features of the system in which our project/initiative is operating?
- Generate awareness and accountability of the project/initiative to societal challenges/responsibilities/constraints of the system.
- Identify the values of the project/initiative in the context of the system – what values does it strive for & wish to maintain?
- Assess the project's/initiative's awareness and accountability of the system and its pursuit of values in the system.

Background and Logic

No project/initiative exists in a vacuum. All multi-actor projects typically have communities in the wider community with/for whom they are seeking to innovate. Projects/initiatives are likely to have particular values in the overall system, which they wish to maintain and further through their activities.

This is a tool that takes a participatory approach to developing a systems schematic. The systems schematic incorporates policy context; main operational themes; key actors; actions; 'horizon' outcomes etc. Once these are identified at an early stage in a project/initiative, the data in the schematic can be periodically revisited as required.

This tool can be used with Tool#1, which maps actors to be involved; Tool#11 & Tool#12, which identify and generate hypotheses in relation to the causes and effects of actions. This tool may also be used with Tool #21, empowerment appraisal because it can be used to raise awareness of constraints surrounding a project/initiative.

Materials

For in person-meetings:

- Sticky notes
- Flipchart paper
- Black markers

For online meetings, an online platform such as Klaxoon or Mural can be used in conjunction with an audio function such as Zoom.

A Graphic Designer may be commissioned to design a systems map, but this is optional.

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

1. Preparation

- Explain the purpose, logic and background of the tool.
- This tool may be building on other tools (such as tool#1 that identifies actors, and tools#11&12 that identify actions). If so, the outcomes of those tools should be put in place for the workshop to implement this tool.
- Note: the outcome of the exercise may be a relatively simple systems 'map' such as in Figure 1, or, in accommodating a larger project, such as Figure 2.

Figure 1: Systems 'map' depicting main themes of activity surrounded by values (leadership, partnerships, independence) and the wider context (climate change, future Teagasc, co-benefits etc.).

Source: Macken-Walsh, Henchion, Regan (in press, 2021)

2. Creation of the Systems Map

A flexible approach is taken in the development of the systems map, which accommodates diversity across different initiatives/projects.

The main prompt questions for the discussion are:

- What are our main areas of activity/our main themes?
 - » What are the actions (and associated actors and stakeholders)
 - » Note: some of all of this brainstorming may be completed in advance and revisited to address the below
- How do these areas of activity/main themes relate to the 'outside world' thinking globally as well as nationally.
 - » Do we have particular responsibilities?
 - » What factors may constrain our achievements (optionally using the empowerment appraisal Tool #21 at this step)?
 - » What are our values in relation to how our activities link with the global picture?
 - » What is our desired legacy?

- Participants are invited to write on sticky notes, shown in the below images, and cluster them into themes/clusters for greater manageability of content.
- Participants use the information written on sticky notes to build their own systems map, illustrating the key thematic areas of activity, how they connect with the outside system, and the key values to be pursued.
- Not all information needs to be portrayed in the systems map (e.g. actions/actors/stakeholders), but it is important that the information is considered in the creation of the systems map. Any information not used can be retained and referred to in future discussions.

3. Use of Systems Map for Assessment

- The systems map is a graphical representation of the main project/initiative themes (areas of intervention); connections with the wider/global picture; and values of the initiative/project to be maintained (possibly as a legacy)
- It should be revisited periodically to assess the extent to which the project/initiative is maintaining a focus on the 'systems' (wider) perspective
- The map can be used to revisit the constraints identified, to 'keep check' that project/initiative actors are maintaining a focus on these constraints (and their mitigation)
- The map can be used to revisit the identified values/ legacy of the project, to 'keep check' that the project/initiative actors are 'keeping check' and mindful of the values/legacy.

Selected snapshots from the co-creation process developing a systems 'map'.

